

ENHANCING THE DAMAGE TOLERANCE OF SRPP/CFPP HYBRID COMPOSITES VIA A BIO-INSPIRED DESIGN

Lorenzo Mencattelli^{1*}, Jun Tang², Yentl Swolfs², Larissa Gorbatikh², Silvestre T. Pinho¹

¹Department of Aeronautics, Imperial College London, London, UK, l.mencattelli@imperial.ac.uk

²Department of Materials Engineering, KU Leuven, Leuven, Belgium, jun.tang@kuleuven.be

Keywords: Hybrid, Damage tolerance, Fracture toughness, Bio-inspired, Failure

ABSTRACT

In this paper, we examine the fracture toughness of a self-reinforced polypropylene/carbon fibre polypropylene cross-ply hybrid laminate and design techniques to enhance two damage tolerance requirements: (i) the energy dissipation capability via promoting sub-critical diffused damage and (ii) the damage tolerance to impact. For this purpose, we micro-engineered the architecture of the composite via tailoring two patterns of discontinuities in the form of laser-cuts across the fibres of the carbon-fibre plies to meet each specific requirement. We performed double edge notched tensile and low velocity impact tests on specimens with engineered microstructures and compared the results against non-engineered specimens. We used the essential work of fracture method to investigate the volumetric energy dissipation capability and the fracture toughness of the hybrid laminates. The DEN-T tests show that hybridising PP tapes with continuous carbon fibres results in a tough material — fracture toughness = 213 kJ/m². The use of tailored pattern of discontinuities managed to successfully delocalise strain concentrations hence greatly increasing the extent of diffused damage. The activation of highly-dissipative sub-critical failure mechanisms, such as pull-outs of CF bundles, has greatly enhanced the energy dissipation of the microstructure, leading to a 90% increase in the slope of the specific work of fracture with respect to the baseline. Engineering the microstructure of impact samples resulted in a 42.7% increase in energy dissipation at a sub-critical level and a 26.6% delay in critical failure, therefore enhancing the impact damage tolerance of the composite.

1 INTRODUCTION

Self-Reinforced Polypropylene (SRPP) belongs to the category of the Self-Reinforced Composites, SRCs [1] and is well known for its outstanding impact resistance [1,2], high strain to failure [1] and fracture toughness [3]. Nonetheless, SRPP is characterised by a low stiffness and relatively low yielding which have limited its use in structural applications. Combining carbon fibres with SRPP to create SRPP/CFPP hybrid composites provides an attractive trade-off between high stiffness and high strain to failure [4,5]; however, it also embrittles the composite, hence jeopardizing the damage tolerance of the hybrid structure. In this regard, developing successful novel strategies aiming at enhancing the damage tolerance of SRPP/CFPP hybrid composites is a challenge not fully addressed up to now, yet of fundamental importance to promote the use of SRPP/CFPP hybrid composites in engineering applications.

Previous investigations on the tensile behaviour of CFPP/SRPP hybrid composites have shown that the embrittlement of the composite due to the presence of carbon fibres leads to damage localisation and unstable damage growth, resulting in stress drops of increasing magnitude as the volume fraction of carbon fibres increases [5,6]. Studies on the penetration impact response of SRPP/CFPP hybrid composites with discontinuous carbon fibres showed that the energy dissipated by the composite decreases with increasing the volume fraction of carbon fibres [7]. This results in a more brittle behaviour of the hybrid composite, characterized by a lower load-bearing capability with impact energy being dissipated after the onset of critical failure (peak-load in the load-displacement curve) [7]. In addition, the penetration occurs at lower indentation depths compared to SRPP laminates [7], hence reducing the damage tolerance of the composite.

Biomimetics has proven to be a powerful tool to improve the damage tolerance of industrial composite materials [8–11]. Specifically, the creation of discontinuities across the load-carrying fibres inspired by bone [12] and nacre-like microstructures [13] has successfully led to enhancing the fracture toughness of thin-ply CFRPs [10], promoting crack deflection and crack diffusion failure mechanisms in CFRPs [11] and stabilising the tensile response of SRPP/CFPP composites [14].

Based on the above, we started a new international collaboration between Imperial College London (UK) and KU Leuven (Belgium), where we sought to combine unique expertise and capabilities in each institution to address the challenge described. Specifically, we tailored two patterns of discontinuities across the load carrying fibres of CFPP plies to improve two damage tolerance requirements of a SRPP/CFPP continuous fibre cross-ply hybrid laminate: (i) the energy dissipation capability via promoting sub-critical diffused damage and (ii) the damage tolerance to impact. We obtained a measure of toughness of the SRPP/CFPP composites and related energy dissipation capability by using the Essential Work of Fracture method [15–18] and DEN-T tests. In addition, we conducted low-velocity penetration impact tests to study the behaviour of the hybrid composites under impact. We tested baseline (no laser-cuts) and engineered configurations.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Basic constituents

We manufactured two configurations, baseline (no-laser cuts) and engineered (with laser-cuts) for DEN-T and impact tests, respectively. Fig.1 shows the schematic of the stacking sequence and geometry for DEN-T and impact samples. We adopted a symmetrical odd (SO) cross-ply configuration with the following stacking sequence $[P/R/P/C_{0^\circ}/P/R/P/C_{90^\circ}/P/R]_{s_0}$ where R refers to a polypropylene tape (overfed twill 2/2 weave with areal density 130 g/m^2), P refers to a polypropylene film of the same grade as the PP tapes and C refers to unidirectional carbon fibre layers (T700SC-50C) prepregged with two polypropylene films.

Figure 1: Schematic of SRPP/CFPP laminate lay-up with details of laser-cut patterns tailored for impact and DEN-T samples. The two laser-cut patterns were designed aiming at optimizing the respective damage tolerance requirement.

Figure 2: SEM image of a laser-cut on a CFPP prepreg ply. The image highlights the high precision of the laser-milling technique adopted. Each cut resulted in a constant thickness (15 μm) and neat cut-ends (tip radius of 7.5 μm).

Firstly, we hot pressed the unidirectional preforms of carbon fibres with two PP layers. This was carried out using a Fontijne Grotnes LabPro 400 press, preheated at 188 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. A surface pressure of 5 bar was applied for 5 min and then cooled down to 40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. in 5 min. Subsequently, we created the patterns of discontinuities by performing laser-cuts on the prepregged CFPP plies. This was obtained by means of a micro-machining system. The high precision of the laser-milling guaranteed an excellent quality of the cuts (see Fig. 2) and high repeatability. In the last step we laid-up the laminate and hot-compacted the plate at 188 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ with a surface pressure of 39 bar for 5 min. The plate cooled down to 40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in 5 min. The thickness of the hot-compacted plates ranged between 1.14 mm and 1.18 mm with a carbon volume fraction of 14%. We cut DEN-T samples (210 mm x 30 mm) and impact samples (110 mm x 110 mm) by mean of a bandsaw. Regarding the DEN-T samples, we notched them using a razor blade, creating a sharp tip with a radius of 125 μm and manufactured DEN-T samples for the baseline and engineered configuration, with evenly spaced ligament lengths from 5 mm to 19 mm. Regarding the impact samples, we manufactured 3 samples for the baseline and engineered configuration, respectively.

2.2 The Essential Work of Fracture (EWF) and DEN-T tests

We conducted DEN-T tests on an Instron 5567 with a displacement rate of 2 mm/min and a gauge length of 120 mm. We recorded both samples surface with two cameras to monitor progressive damage evolution during test. We adopted the essential work of fracture method to evaluate the performances of baseline and engineered configuration in terms of fracture toughness and energy dissipation capacity.

The EWF method requires the calculation of the work of fracture (W_{fracture}) as the integral of the load vs. displacement curve for each sample with ligament length (l), see Fig. 1:

$$W_{\text{fracture}} = W_{\text{essential}} + W_{\text{plastic}} \quad (1)$$

where $W_{\text{essential}}$ is the energy dissipated at the fracture plane and W_{plastic} is the energy dissipated in the volume of the sample, i.e. the ‘plastic’ region. Following the assumption that the ‘plastic’ region scales with the square of the ligament length [18], Eq. 1 can be rewritten as follows:

$$W_{\text{fracture}} = w_{\text{essential}} * lt + \beta w_{\text{plastic}} * l^2 t \quad (2)$$

$$w_{\text{fracture}} = \frac{W_{\text{fracture}}}{lt} = w_{\text{essential}} + \beta w_{\text{plastic}} * l \quad (3)$$

with $w_{\text{essential}}$ being an energy per unit surface, w_{plastic} an energy per unit volume, t the sample thickness and β a shape factor of the ‘plastic’ region. $w_{\text{essential}}$ is a measure of fracture toughness and βw_{plastic} , i.e. the slope of the specific work of fracture (w_{fracture}) is a measure of energy dissipation capacity of the structure.

2.3 Penetration impact tests

We conducted low-velocity penetration impact tests on baseline and engineered samples using a drop-weight tower. The samples were impacted with a mass of 26.17 kg and an energy of 256.7 J. Each sample was clamped with a circular clamp of 60 mm outer diameter and 40 mm inner diameter. As performance indicator of the impact tests, we quantified the energy absorbed before and after the peak load, i.e. the area under the load vs displacement curve.

3 RESULTS

3.1 DEN-T tests results

Fig. 3 shows a comparison between two samples of baseline and engineered configuration with equal ligament length ($l=15$ mm). The figure highlights the smooth damage growth of the engineered microstructure. The highly expanded sub-critical damage (whitening in Fig. 3) initially formed in areas away from the ligament plane and subsequently migrated towards the ligament plane, until final failure occurred.

Fig. 4a shows the photograph of baseline and engineered samples with similar ligament length at similar applied displacement. The whitening in the photographs correlates with damage developing in the SRPP layers in the form of debonding, plastic deformation and fibrillation. Fig. 4b shows the trend-lines of the specific work of fracture calculated using the EWF. The linear trend-lines represent the data very well ($R^2 > 0.9$). Fig. 4b highlights the large increase in slope of the specific work of fracture of the engineered configuration with respect to the baseline.

3.2 Impact tests results

Fig. 5a shows the load vs displacement curves of the engineered and baseline samples. The load vs displacement curves of the two configurations show good reproducibility. The load-drop of the engineered samples, corresponding to the onset of critical damage, was delayed to larger applied displacements — 26.6% average increase. The statistical significance of this figure was verified by calculating the associated p -value, which was found to be 0.0305, i.e. statistically significant (using a standard threshold of 0.05). Additionally, the energy dissipated before the drop-load was increased of 42.7% in the engineered configuration with respect to the baseline (statistically significant increase, p -value=0.0005). Fig. 5b shows the impact surface of two representative baseline and engineered samples, highlighting the diffused sub-critical damage developed in the engineered configuration (whitening in Fig. 5b).

Figure 3: Comparison between two representative samples of baseline and engineered configurations with the same ligament length ($l=15 \text{ mm}$). The failure process of the engineered sample was characterized by a highly stable damage growth (extended plateau in the load vs displacement curve). The photographs show the damage in the engineering configuration recorded at subsequent instants during the test. Damage was initially delocalised from the ligament plane and it subsequently migrated towards the ligament plane until final failure of the sample.

Figure 4: (a) The image shows two photographs of engineered and baseline samples with similar ligament length ($l=17 \text{ mm}$) taken at similar applied displacements. The whitening refers to plastic deformation, debonding and fibrillation of the PP tapes. For a similar applied displacement, while the baseline sample had already catastrophically failed with most of damage being localized around the ligament plane, the engineered samples showed sub-critical accumulation of damage extensively diffused away from the ligament plane. (b) The comparison between the specific work of fracture of baseline and engineered configurations reveals a great increase in volumetric energy absorption capability of the engineered configuration with this effect being increasingly significant as the ligament length increases.

Figure 5: (a) The load vs. displacement curves of engineered and baseline samples showing how the introduction of laser-cuts in the engineered configuration locally tailored the stiffness of the composite and promoted sub-critical accumulation of damage (energy absorbed before the peak-load). This resulted in a great delay in critical failure (26% on average). (b) The two photographs of the impact surface of a baseline and an engineered sample highlight the larger extent of whitening, i.e. subcritical damage, developed in the engineered sample.

4 DISCUSSION

Fig. 3 shows that the tailored pattern of laser-cuts was successful in delocalising strain concentration, hence promoting a highly stable failure process (plateau in the load vs displacement curve of the engineered sample). Contrarily to the brittle failure of the baseline, characterised by a large load-drop, the engineered microstructure was able to preserve most of its load bearing capability during damage growth. This was achieved via the extensive sub-critical accumulation of damage in the form of plastic deformation of the PP tape, PP debonding and carbon fibre bundle pull-outs. The subcritical damage initially formed in regions of the sample away from the ligament plane. Subsequently, the subcritical damage gradually migrated towards the ligament plane as shown in Fig. 5a. This protected the ligament plane from a catastrophic failure, hence delaying final failure. The delay in catastrophic failure is also evident from the observation of the photograph of a baseline and engineered samples with same ligament length taken at a similar applied displacement (see Fig. 4a). Fig. 4a shows that while the baseline had already reached the final failure of the sample, damage in the engineered configuration was still diffusing at a sub-critical level.

The stable, highly dissipative failure process of the engineered microstructure resulted in an increase of about 90% of the slope of the specific work of fracture ($w_{fracture}$) with respect to the baseline configuration.

Even though the slope of $w_{fracture}$ depends on the geometry of the sample, since the two configurations have the same geometry, the comparison between engineered and baseline configurations holds true. Therefore, the large increase in slope can be regarded as an effective increase in energy dissipation capability of the structure. Therefore, in a design space where damage tolerance is a driving requirement, high values of both $\beta w_{plastic}$ and $w_{essential}$ are of fundamental importance.

Figure 6: $\beta w_{plastic}$ and $w_{essential}$ comparison of polymers, polymer blends, polymer composites tested using DEN-T tests at 2 mm/min displacement rate and the essential work of fracture [19]. The large dots refer to the two SRPP/CFPP hybrid composites tested in this work. Hybridising PP tapes with carbon fibre resulted in a tough material whose volumetric energy dissipation capability was greatly enhanced via the introduction of discontinuities in the form of laser-cuts.

In order to compare the performances in terms of fracture toughness and energy dissipation capability of the SRPP/CFPP hybrid composites designed in this work against other materials gathered from literature, we gathered the values of $\beta w_{plastic}$ and $w_{essential}$ of several polymers, polymer blends, micro- and macro- composites. The comparison reported in Fig. 6 shows that: (i) the effect of combining PP tapes with carbon fibres resulted in an excellent value of fracture toughness and good energy dissipation capability; (ii) the design of tailored laser-cut patterns successfully improved the energy dissipation capability of the hybrid SRPP/CFPP composite, thereby enhancing the damage tolerance of the material.

The impact test results in terms of load vs displacement reported in Fig. 5a show that we successfully delayed critical failure (peak load) at larger applied displacements. The critical displacement was found to be 26.6% higher in the engineered configuration than in the baseline. This figure was statistically significant (p -value = 0.0305, calculated with the One-sample t-test and a 5% significance level). The tailored laser-cut pattern promoted delocalisation of strain concentrations, thereby leading to highly diffused sub-critical damage (whitening in Fig. 5b). This has resulted in an increase in dissipated energy prior to the peak load, i.e. at subcritical levels, in the engineered configuration with respect to the baseline of 42.7% (p -value = 0.0005). The analysis of the fracture surface of two representative baseline and engineered impact samples in Fig. 7 reveals a major difference in the failure process: while the baseline configuration was characterised by short pull-out of broken carbon fibres, the engineered configuration was dominated by pull-outs of large carbon fibre bundles, pulled out from the laser-cuts. The large pull-outs of the engineered configuration resulted in a large portion of the total absorbed energy being dissipated at subcritical levels, therefore increasing the impact damage tolerance of the SRPP/CFPP hybrid composite.

Figure 7: Photographs and optical micrographies of the impact surface of two representative baseline and engineered impact samples. The large carbon fibre pull-outs characteristic of the engineered configuration allowed for the activation of a sub-critical highly dissipative damage mechanism that resulted in a large portion of energy (42.7%) being dissipated before critical failure had occurred.

5 CONCLUSIONS

For the first time in the literature, we were able to assess the excellent toughness of SRPP/CFPP hybrid composites – 213 kJ/m^2 , and its good energy dissipation capability (slope of the specific work of fracture – 17.9 MJ/m^3). We show that the use of a point-by-point technique to engineer the microstructure, such as the use of laser-cuts across the load carrying fibres of the composite, can greatly enhance the energy diffusion capability of the hybrid structure. This is achieved by promoting extensive diffused damage at a sub-critical level, leading to an overall increase in energy dissipation capability of the structure of 90%.

The penetration impact tests revealed that the use of discontinuities successfully delocalises damage. This, in combination with the locally-tailored stiffness, leads to a significant delay in critical failure in the engineered configuration with respect to the baseline. The energy dissipated at subcritical levels, i.e. before the peak load, was found to be significantly larger in the engineered configuration – 42.7% higher than the baseline – therefore leading to an enhancement in impact damage tolerance.

To conclude, we have shown that we can successfully design micro-engineered structures via tailoring laser-cut patterns to meet different damage tolerance requirements at different locations within the same structure, using the same technique to engineer the microstructure and the same material system. Therefore, this technique allows to greatly expand the design space of engineering structures and provides engineers with the opportunity of creating solutions of relevant industrial impact.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 722626 is gratefully acknowledged. fibremodproject.eu. Yentl Swolfs acknowledges FWO Flanders for his postdoctoral fellowship. Silvestre Taveira Pinho also acknowledges funding from the EPSRC under grant EP/M002500/1. Lorenzo Mencattelli gratefully acknowledges the Institution of Mechanical Engineers (IMEchE) for covering part of the Conference ICCM22 travel costs via the Thomas Andrew Common Grants scheme.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Kmetty, T. Bárány, and J. Karger-Kocsis, "Self-reinforced polymeric materials: A review," *Progress in Polymer Science (Oxford)*, vol. 35, no. 10, pp. 1288–1310, 2010.
- [2] Y. Meerten, Y. Swolfs, J. Baets, L. Gorbatikh, and I. Verpoest, "Penetration impact testing of self-reinforced composites," *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 68, pp. 289–295, 2015.
- [3] A. Stocchi, V. Pettarin, A. Izer, T. Bárány, T. Czigány, and C. Bernal, "Fracture behavior of recyclable all-polypropylene composites composed of α - And β -modifications," *Journal of Thermoplastic Composite Materials*, vol. 24, no. 6, pp. 805–818, 2011.
- [4] I. Taketa, J. Ustarroz, L. Gorbatikh, S. V. Lomov, and I. Verpoest, "Interply hybrid composites with carbon fiber reinforced polypropylene and self-reinforced polypropylene," *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 41, no. 8, pp. 927–932, 2010.
- [5] Y. Swolfs *et al.*, "Tensile behaviour of intralayer hybrid composites of carbon fibre and self-reinforced polypropylene," *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 59, pp. 78–84, 2014.
- [6] Y. Swolfs, Y. Meerten, P. Hine, I. Ward, I. Verpoest, and L. Gorbatikh, "Introducing ductility in hybrid carbon fibre/self-reinforced composites through control of the damage mechanisms," *Composite Structures*, vol. 131, pp. 259–265, 2015.
- [7] M. Selezneva *et al.*, "The brittle-to-ductile transition in tensile and impact behavior of hybrid carbon fibre/self-reinforced polypropylene composites," *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 109, pp. 20–30, 2018.
- [8] L. Mencattelli and S. T. Pinho, "Realising bio-inspired impact damage tolerant thin-ply CFRP Bouligand structures via promoting diffused sub critical helicoidal damage," *Composites Science and Technology*, submitted in August 2018.
- [9] L. Mencattelli, J. Tang, Y. Swolfs, L. Gorbatikh, and S. T. Pinho, "Bio-inspired design for enhanced damage tolerance of self-reinforced polypropylene/carbon fibre polypropylene hybrid composites," *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 121, pp. 341–352, 2019.
- [10] G. Bullegas, S. T. Pinho, and S. Pimenta, "Engineering the translaminar fracture behaviour of thin-ply composites," *Composites Science and Technology*, vol. 131, pp. 110–122, 2016.
- [11] F. Narducci, K.-Y. Lee, and S. T. Pinho, "Realising damage-tolerant nacre-inspired CFRP," *Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids*, vol. 116, pp. 391–402, 2018.
- [12] H. Gao, "Application of fracture mechanics concepts to hierarchical biomechanics of bone and bone-like materials," *International Journal of Fracture*, vol. 138, no. 1, p. 101, 2006.
- [13] R. Rabiei, S. Bekah, and F. Barthelat, "Failure mode transition in nacre and bone-like materials," *Acta Biomaterialia*, vol. 6, pp. 4081–4089, 2010.
- [14] J. Tang *et al.*, "Discontinuities as a way to influence the failure mechanisms and tensile performance of hybrid carbon fiber/self-reinforced polypropylene composites," *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 107, pp. 354–365, 2018.
- [15] K. B. Broberg, "Crack-growth criteria and non-linear fracture mechanics," *Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids*, vol. 19, no. 6, pp. 407–418, 1971.

- [16] K. B. Broberg, "On stable crack growth," *Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids*, vol. 23, no. 3, pp. 215–237, 1975.
- [17] K. B. Broberg, "Critical review of some methods in nonlinear fracture mechanics," *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, vol. 50, no. 2, pp. 157–164, 1995.
- [18] Y. Mai, S. Wong, and X. Chen, "Application of fracture mechanics for characterization of toughness of polymer blends," in *Polymer blends: formulations and performance, Vol 2.*, D. Paul and C. Bucknall, Eds. New York: Wiley, 2000, pp. 17–58.
- [19] T. Bárány, T. Czigány, and J. Karger-Kocsis, "Application of the essential work of fracture (EWF) concept for polymers, related blends and composites: A review," *Progress in Polymer Science*, vol. 35, no. 10, pp. 1257–1287, 2010.